

Appendix Table 5. White-tailed deer element percentages for selected structures.

Structures selected for Tables 2-7 include those with the highest numbers of specific taxa, as well as a range of building types.

	Q-54 hall	Q-162 temple	Q-97 hall	Q-58 temple	Q-92 house	R-106 palace	R-112 house
carpal	0.1%	0.3%	0.6%	0.4%		0.2%	
limb	5.7%	14.8%	5.7%	10.1%	29.3%	14.6%	3.9%
metapodial/phalanges	19.4%	12.9%	18.2%	23.1%	20.4%	25.3%	23.2%
patella	0.2%	0.7%	0.2%	0.4%	0.1%	0.7%	
pelvis	8.8%	7.6%	9.8%	4.8%	3.3%	10.9%	5.8%
rib	3.9%	4.0%	5.0%	2.3%	7.7%	2.8%	5.8%
shoulder	3.8%	2.3%	4.0%	3.3%	1.2%	0.2%	1.9%
skull	1.2%	9.6%	0.7%	2.6%	3.3%		3.2%
tarsal	8.9%	10.6%	8.8%	9.8%	6.2%	10.0%	6.5%
upper limb	17.0%	15.0%	13.9%	13.3%	8.7%	14.2%	11.0%
upper limb lower	16.7%	10.6%	14.1%	13.5%	8.9%	11.1%	9.7%
vertebra	14.3%	11.7%	19.0%	16.3%	10.9%	10.0%	29.0%